

populations were seeded in 1992 dry season (DS) on 2 Mar to allow segregation for photoperiod sensitivity.

Photoperiod-insensitive and -sensitive plants segregated in a 3:1 ratio, indicating that a single dominant gene

governs photoperiod sensitivity in all three crosses (see table). We classified the segregants that flowered until Aug as photoperiod-insensitive and those that flowered in Sep and later as photoperiod-sensitive. In 1992 WS, desirable

photoperiod-sensitive ms segregants were crossed with respective recurrent parents to get BC₁F₁ generation. The scheme for developing photoperiod-sensitive ms lines is presented in the figure. ■

Isolation of maintainers and restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines

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We crossed 21 short- and medium-duration indica cultivars with eight CMS lines (see table) during Jul-Oct 1990 to identify maintainers and restorers. F₁ hybrids were grown in the field during Nov 1991-Feb 1992.

Pollen sterility was determined from florets in the upper third of the panicle before dehiscence; pollen grains were stained with I₂-KI. Cultivars with >95% pollen and spikelet sterility were classified as potential maintainers; those

with 5-95%, as partial restorers; and those with <5%, as effective restorers. Maintainers were more frequent than restorers (see table).

IR62829 A/Co 45, IR62829 A/Co 43, IR58025 A/IR50, MS37 A/IET11752, and Mangala A/IR62 had 100% pollen

sterility. These crosses are being used in a backcross program to develop new CMS lines. Co 43, Heera, and MS210 were identified as restorers (see table) and are being used to develop new hybrid combinations. ■

Restorers and maintainers for CMS lines. Coimbatore, India, 1991-92.

CMS line ^a	Potential maintainers	Effective restorers	Partial restorers
IR62829 A (100.0)	Co 43, Co 45	-	ADT36
IR58025 A (99.7)	IR50	Co 43	T2099, 3043, Co 45, IET7511, Aruna
TNAU1 A (99.5)	Co 45, MO 9	Co 43	4308, TM4309, Annada, MO 7
V20 A (100)	TM4309, IR60	-	Co 43
IR46828 A (99.2)	-	Heera	-
MS37 A (99.8)	IR30864, IET11752	MS210	-
IR54755 A (98.9)	IET11752	-	-
Mangala A (99.6)	IR62	-	-

^aFigures in parentheses show spikelet sterility under bagged conditions.

Grain quality

An upland rice line with low protein in Japan

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Polished grain from upland rice, which is high in protein and difficult to process, is used mainly for rice crackers in Japan. Processors have been eager for the development of a lower protein upland rice.

1. Correlation between leaf chlorophyll and grain protein contents in upland rice lines.

2. Correlation between chlorophyll content of leaf and heading period in upland and lowland-upland crossbred rice lines.

We compared the contents of leaf chlorophyll and protein of polished rice in seven lowland-upland crossbred rice lines. These contents were highly correlated ($r = 0.897^{**}$). Selection for leaf chlorophyll content can therefore be

